

WP2: National policy, legal and service frameworks

Psychosocial Support for Promoting Mental Health and Well-being among
Adolescent Young Carers in Europe: ME-We project, Grant Agreement number
754702

Country-specific report (case study) Italy

Source: <https://sites.google.com/site/fradituri/le-regioni-dell-italia>

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Categories	Results
Specific legislation	In Italy, no specific legislation protecting and supporting young carers and their families exists.
Non-specific legislation National level	<p>Law 23 December 1997, n. 451, http://www.camera.it/parlam/leggi/97451l.htm (Istituzione della Commissione parlamentare per l'infanzia e dell'Osservatorio nazionale per l'infanzia, pubblicata nella Gazzetta Ufficiale n. 302 del 30 dicembre 1997) Establishment of the Parliamentary Committee on Children and the National Observatory for Children. Targeted age group: children (age not specified)</p> <p>Law 28 August 1997, n. 285, http://www.camera.it/parlam/leggi/97285l.htm (Disposizioni per la promozione di diritti e di opportunità per l'infanzia e l'adolescenza, pubblicata nella Gazzetta Ufficiale n. 207 del 5 settembre 1997) Provisions for the promotion of rights and opportunities for childhood and adolescence. Targeted age group: children and adolescents (age not specified)</p> <p>Law 22 June 2016, n. 112, http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/06/24/16G00125/sg (Disposizioni in materia di assistenza in favore delle persone con disabilità grave prive del sostegno familiare) Provisions supporting people with serious disability who do not have support from their parents. Targeted age group: not specified</p> <p>Law 27 December 2017, n. 205, paragraphs 254-255, http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/gu/2017/12/29/302/so/62/sg/pdf (Bilancio di previsione dello Stato per l'anno finanziario 2018 e bilancio pluriennale per il triennio 2018-2020) State budget for year 2018 and for the three-year period 2018-2020. Definition of family caregiver: "The person who assists and takes care of the spouse, of the partner in a civil partnership (between persons of the same sex) or of the cohabiting partner, in accordance with the law of 20 May 2016, n. 76, or of a family member within the second degree, or in the cases indicated by article 33, paragraph 3 of Law 5 February 1992, n. 104, of a family member</p>

within the third degree, who, due to an illness, disability, chronic or degenerative disability is not self-sufficient and able to take care of himself/herself, and is recognised as disabled in need of global, continuous and long-term care on the basis of Article 3, paragraph 3, of the Law 5 February 1992, n. 104 194/1992, or according to Law 11 February 1980, n. 18, establishing the National Attendance Allowance.” (Paragraph 255)

Fund for non self-sufficiency: ”It is established by the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies a Fund for supporting the role of caring and assistance provided by family caregivers, allocating the provision establishes the fund to support the caring and assistance role of family caregiver, allocating € 20 million for each of the years 2018, 2019 and 2020. The Fund is intended for the financing of legislative interventions aimed at recognising the social and economic value of the care activity of family caregivers.” (Paragraph 254)

Targeted age group: not specified

Law 5 February 1992, n. 104, <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/1992/02/17/092G0108/sg> (Legge-quadro per l'assistenza, l'integrazione sociale e i diritti delle persone handicappate)

Provision for the assistance, social integration and rights of people with disabilities.

Psychological support: in cases of physical or mental illness or disability, the family members can benefit from a psychological support service from the Local Health Authority (LHA). There is no age restriction.

Paid leave: any cohabitants' family member within the third degree has the right to a series of benefits, which take the form of the possibility to have 3 days of paid leave per month. These paid leaves can be theoretically requested by anyone, even by minors. Paid leaves are regulated by Art. 33, comma 3, of law 5 February 1992, n. 104.

Targeted age group: not specified

Law 11 February 1980, n. 18, <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/1980/02/14/080U0018/sg> (Indennità di accompagnamento agli invalidi civili totalmente inabili)

Allowances for people with severe disability who are not self-sufficient.

Targeted age group: minors who have severe disability can benefit from this law too. However, family carers are not mentioned.

Law 28 May 2017, n. 71

	<p>http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/atto/serie_generale/caricaDettaglioAtto/originario?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2017-06-03&atto.codiceRedazionale=17G00085&elenco30giorni=false (Disposizioni a tutela dei minori per la prevenzione ed il contrasto del fenomeno del cyberbullismo)</p> <p>Provisions for the protection of minors and for the prevention of cyberbullying.</p> <p>Targeted age group: minors (<18 years old)</p>
<p>Non-specific legislation Regional level</p>	<p>Emilia-Romagna Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2, http://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:legge:2014;2 (Norme per il riconoscimento ed il sostegno del caregiver familiare (persona che presta volontariamente cura e assistenza), pubblicata nel Bollettino Ufficiale n. 93 del 28 marzo 2014)</p> <p>Norms for the recognition and support of the family caregiver.</p> <p>Family caregiver is defined, for the first time in legal terms, as: the person who on a voluntary basis, in a free and responsible way, provides care of a person in conditions of non self-sufficiency or whose disability or health condition necessitates long-term assistance.</p> <p>This law was then taken up by other regions, Abruzzo in 2016 (http://www2.consiglio.regione.abruzzo.it/leggi_tv/abruzzo_lr/2016/lr16043/Articolato.asp) and Campania in 2017 (http://regione.campania.it/normativa/item.php?7b7fec2087f982d694b26f0cc9f850d6=621512db6f270ae41a780e1cce881b25&pgCode=G19I231R1742&id_doc_type=1&id_tema=26&refresh=on). In a further six regions a legal text was filed, taking as reference that of Emilia-Romagna.</p> <p>Targeted age group: not specified</p> <p>Emilia-Romagna Regional Law 30 July 2015, n. 14, http://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?urn=er:assemblealegislativa:legge:2015;14 (Disciplina a sostegno dell'inserimento lavorativo e dell'inclusione sociale delle persone in condizione di fragilità e vulnerabilità, attraverso l'integrazione tra i servizi pubblici del lavoro, sociali e sanitari)</p> <p>Provision to support the job integration and social inclusion of people in conditions of fragility and vulnerability.</p> <p>Targeted age group: not specified</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation National level</p>	<p>Law 27 December 2017, n. 205:</p>

	<p>At the moment there is no law establishing how to use the funding (art. 254 Law 205/2017) to support informal carers (as defined in art. 255 della Legge 205/2017). It might translate into a care allowance provided to the family, or to the non self-sufficient person, so it can support the family and the carer.</p> <p>Law 5 February 1992, n. 104:</p> <p>The 3 days of paid leave can be theoretically requested by anyone, even by the minor who is working. But, in its practical application, due to the fact that there are not so many working minors, the application of this tool it is used especially from the 18th birthday onwards.</p> <p>According to the opinion of one expert, the young carer who lives in a healthy environment is basically ignored by the legal system, set aside the psychological support from the LHA. If, on the contrary, she/he takes care of the entire household, the answer of the legal system is to evaluate if the subjects who should have parental responsibilities are doing their job. According to the current legislation, in the activities targeting youth (and not specifically young carers, who at the moment are not recognised by law) the only available support is the psychological counselling offered by LHA according to law 5 February 1992, n. 104.</p>
<p>Enactment of legislation Regional level</p>	<p>Law 27 December 2017, n. 205, paragraphs 254-255</p> <p>According to the opinion of one expert, 20 million euros a year is not much and now the regions have the possibility to implement targeted and innovative interventions or to reinforce policies they already have. Many of them will probably refinance care allowances.</p> <p>A second expert underlines that, according to art. 254 and 255 of this law, it is only established the general-strategic aim of the law: the recognition of the role and function of carers. To be able to use the resources of the Fund (art. 254) to support carers (as defined from art. 255) it is necessary to wait for specific regulations which are not available yet.</p> <p>Emilia-Romagna Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2</p> <p>In Emilia-Romagna the "Deliberazione della giunta regionale" 16 June, n. 858 (http://bur.regione.emilia-romagna.it/dettaglio-inserzione?i=aba33f088caa45c781e2755504e89925) defines the implementation methods of the Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2, concerning the recognition and enhancement of family carers. In the implementation guidelines the general concept of caregivers has been extended, and specific areas and clarifications concerning young carers have been included. The decision of including a broader age range was based on the high percentage of young people who reported to be NEETs because of caring activities in their family.</p>

	In Abruzzo and Campania no implementation guidelines have been issued.
Changes in legislation	The introduction of provisions like the Law 27 December 2017, n. 205 was supported by some family associations. In Italy carers are defined in legal terms starting from the law of the Emilia-Romagna Region of 2014. At the national level, the path started at the beginning of 2017, with the discussion at the Senate Labour Commission (i.e. Labour and Social Security Commission (11th) of the Italian Senate) of three draft laws. One of these was filed by Senator Angioni in the Senate and by Honorable Patriarca in the Chamber of Deputies, on the basis of the experience made in Emilia-Romagna.
Specific policy and service frameworks (only available on local level)	Possibility of personalisation of the study plan: derives from experiences made by a school in Cesena, which used the BES/SEN (Bisogni Educativi Speciali/Special Educational Needs, http://www.miur.gov.it/bisogni-educativi-speciali). This tool allows, for example, more flexibility concerning the school attendance plan or the expected attainments for young carers.
Non-specific policy and service frameworks Regional level	In Emilia-Romagna logistical facilitations for participation in university studies can be provided. The online course of study, which allows for study at home, has been greatly expanded. In relation to the job market, the “Patto regionale per il lavoro” (http://formazioneilavoro.regione.emilia-romagna.it/patto-per-il-lavoro) in Emilia-Romagna has a specific reference to the importance of caring work.
Non-specific policy and service frameworks Local level	None mentioned.
Enactment of policy and service frameworks Regional level	The funds are allocated to the regions and then they are autonomous in using them, but often there is no concrete return of information. When the funds are allocated to the regions, they are distributed on the basis of very general programmes, after which there is not always a detailed analysis on how these funds are used.
Enactment of policy and service frameworks Local level	The quality of social services provided in Italy (including those aimed to the protection of children at risk) can really vary from place to place, also between realities that are in fact geographically close. As a consequence, to the same case there can be a very inefficient response in one place and a good practice in another.
Changes in policy and service frameworks (only available on regional)	In the regional Commission set up for developing the implementation guidelines of the Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2, were included representatives of the regional educational institution. For the university context, collaboration with the Regional Agency for the Right to Education has been active since two years.

level)	
Recognition of young carers (only available on regional level)	<p>The Regional Determination 16 June 2017, number 858 (http://bur.regione.emilia-romagna.it/dettaglio-inserzione?i=aba33f088caa45c781e2755504e89925) defines the implementation methods concerning the recognition and enhancement of family carers of the Emilia-Romagna Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2.</p> <p>In the implementation guidelines of the Emilia-Romagna Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2, the caregiver's skills are recognised. Moreover, it is emphasized that educational institutions can enhance the status of caregivers in accordance with current legislation on training credits (http://www.istruzione.it/urp/credito_scolastico_formativo.shtml).</p>
Key strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement of family associations, which resulted in provisions like the Law 27 December 2017, n. 205 - There are virtuous realities (best practices) where families are under control and social services intervene, if needed, acting on the prevention and support - Involvement of regional stakeholders (i.e. representative of the Regional School Office) in developing the implementation guidelines of the Regional Law 28 March 2014, n. 2 - Agreements between stakeholders for the recognition of young carers (i.e. protocol signed with the Ministry of Education, University and Research)
Key limitations National level	<p>General limitations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Italy is one of the EU countries without an ad hoc legislation on family caregivers - Lack of resources: there are barriers of staff and costs - Lack of awareness: this is a topic so far that has not received the attention of the ministerial structures, nor of professionals. There is not an adequate recognition of the impact that such situations have on a young carer. - Lack of a definition: the young person providing care is not defined as a caregiver, but as a minor in adversity - Social services often do not act in a preventive way and intervene only once something striking happens - The judiciary system often tends to apply the concept of "best interest of the child" to grow up in a healthy context by considering safer to remove her/him from the compromised household instead of providing supports to allow her/him to stay in the family. <p>Limitations of the Law 5 February 1992, n. 104:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The three days of paid leave do not allow family carers to manage the situation; they do not provide "real" and "concrete" support - Only carers who are working can benefit from the paid leave

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - This law has been interpreted in a quite restrictive way <p>Limitations of the Law 27 December 2017, n. 205:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The fund to support the caring and assistance role of family carers is not high, considering that it is for the financial coverage of interventions aimed at recognizing the social and economic value of family caregivers and the number of potential beneficiaries is high compared to the available resources.
<p>Key limitations</p> <p>Regional level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of a formalized national coordination. There are regions which are well-organized, while others do not function well. The disparity in the different territorial areas of the country as regards welfare systems, social services and primary care system, impacts differently on the possibility of giving help and support to both young carers and caregivers in general. - Unequal allocation of resources between North and South. - According to one expert, some regions do not have the necessary skills to build innovative programmes and projects and therefore have the tendency to take experiences and regulations already elaborated and adopted in other regional contexts - Criticalities in the administration of some regions, which are back on the application of norms. This leads to a lack of investment in new programmes.
<p>Key limitations</p> <p>Local level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of resources in some municipalities - Social services procedures are sometimes complicated and not child-friendly, so when a young carer tries to navigate the system to support his/her family might find it too complicated and decide to give up
<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p>National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The financial support, without other strategies is not enough (vision “no cash-for-care, but services for care”). Family carers also need services, and all the activities with the Fund for self-sufficiency were aimed exactly at encouraging the creation of a system of services that would help families to manage this kind of situation. - Lack of awareness: this is a topic that so far has not received enough attention. It would be necessary to reflect and discuss more the issue of young carers. - According to one expert, the tribunals are sometimes strict in interpreting the “best interest of the child” to growing up in a healthy environment as removing her/him from the household. A support intervention to keep him/her in the household, which sometimes could be a solution, is often not pursued as it is considered more risky and less predictable in terms of human and economic resources to be applied. - The effects that such situations have on young carers have not been evaluated yet - The society is aging and this means that caring activities are part of everyone’s life. The State has to establish support for family caregivers.

<p>Evaluation of the current situation</p> <p>Regional level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – According to the opinion of one expert, due to criticalities in the administration some regions will probably use the funds to refinance care allowances and not to implement targeted and innovative interventions
<p>Attitudes to existing policy responses</p>	<p>The important result achieved with the involvement of the MIUR (Ministry of Education, University and Research), which represents a first level of national involvement on the issue of young carers, was assessed very positively. This is because the Ministry recognises that “this problem exists” and that it is necessary to help young people who are attending schools and experiencing these issues.</p>
<p>Suggested changes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – On the 17th of October 2018 the Senate Commission for Labour and Social Security has started the examination of 5 Law Proposals (DDL) concerning informal care and it is in the process of auditing different stakeholders (i.e. carers organizations) to collect their opinions. However, it is impossible to foresee time, modalities and results of the discussion and approval process of the DDLs. It is important to remark that all of them recognise the existence of students young carers in Italy who are performing a socially relevant care activity who should be recognised with a credit to facilitate their educational process. – A national law: the same legal framework in the whole country, which, if needed, is applied differently from region to region – Raise awareness through an awareness campaign in schools and then towards professionals working in social, health and education sectors – Collect more data on the percentage of young carers and families living in this kind of situation, in order to show that this is a relevant issue – A specific law with situation-specific solutions, addressing the issue case by case (depending on the kind of care activity that is provided, for whom, for how long, etc.). The legal provisions should establish who intervenes, how they intervene and which specific tools can be used. After that, the application of the legal provision should be carried out by specific units. – Create a place for discussion and involving the following stakeholders: the Department for Family Policies, the Ministry of Labour, the MIUR – Officially recognise the value of young carers, during the study period and also beyond that, e.g. one of the experts suggests that the time devoted to caring activities could be economically compensated, as it happens for instance for the civil service – Tax deductions in addition to care allowances – Strengthen local support services – Adapt existing legislation, e.g. by officially recognizing young carers within the Law 5 February 1992, n. 104

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Caregiving should be recognised by the health sector as a form of distress for carers
<p>Future goals and hopes National level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A national legislation on caregivers with specific attention to the problems and needs of young carers, and to actions of support for them - Definition of the profile followed by targeted interventions: young carers should receive adequate support in cases where they live problems related to their care responsibility. The support should be adequate to their age and to the problems and situations they experience. - Incentives for employers, who hire teleworking caregivers with part-time working hours. These are part of a draft law (http://www.handylex.org/gun/caregiver_testo_unificato_senato.shtml#testo_unificato). - A contact person (e.g. a teacher in a school, a social worker in social services) with deep knowledge on the problems affecting young carers and the necessary tools. Such professionals should be available in schools and social services, where actions aimed at supporting and helping both the young carer and the person in need of help should be implemented. - A social service that monitors the family and reacts promptly - More interconnections between services (e.g. schools) and policy areas - Increase awareness about the positive effects of caring activities: “providing care is an element leading to build skills, to develop the ability to face situations and conflicts and to build relationships with others” [13] - It would be helpful to constantly monitor the situation of young carers in Italy
<p>Future goals and hopes Regional level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fewer differences among regions in the distribution of funds: the hope is that the regions can improve their knowledge and competences and, in this way, create more innovative intervention for young carers and then continue also with regional resources. - The approval of Regional Laws to recognise and support informal carers, based on the good practices already existing in some Regions.